

Rentolog Electric Water Technology

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ABSTRACT

When electricity passes through the system, the electron in the system becomes unstable. sodium ion is highly electronegative, the electron in sodium will pass through aluminum foil but gets trapped in the silicon and elephant grass electrolyte. Grass absorbs photon light from the sun in the process of photosynthesis but in this way the grass will store the electrons from electricity as photoelectric and also silicon is a good conductor for electricity, therefore electrons can feel comfortable in that region. Similarly, the zinc will tend to sacrifice its electron because it is a highly active metal. but it will also be trapped in the electrolyte. Also, fiber grass will block the electron from going out of the system till when it is needed. After it is successful charged, you can connect your phone and the electron stored in the electrolyte will charge them.

INTRODUCTION

The world in general is advancing fast and the use of fuel is gradually going out of the market, lithium battery can no longer sustain the environment in terms of fossil fuel consumption and also people has loss their lives as a result manhandle of lithium battery. These are its laps

1. Lithium-ion batteries are not fitting for pretty severe usages as they do not hold much sturdy technology. Since Li-ion batteries have liquid polymerized electrolytes inside, these batteries can become perforated quickly with minimum force.
2. This lithium-ion battery disadvantage has come to the force in modern years. Many airlines restrict the intake of lithium-ion batteries, and hence their freight is limited to ships. Also, for air passengers, these lithium-ion batteries usually require to stay in carry-on baggage.
3. Although with the safety position, this may vary from time to time. However, the number of batteries remains limited and this is what is the most prominent disadvantage of lithium-ion batteries.
4. Another principal disadvantage of lithium-ion batteries is that they are not safe to use at higher temperatures. Also, in the case of smartphones that overheat, li-ion batteries can become explosive and catch fire. Even though electronic controllers get used to regulating the temperature, these batteries are pretty unsafe to use in transportable device.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Your number one agricultural base battery has been analyzed and chosen as a preferable choice over all batteries

1. Zinc makes a great choice for a sacrificial anode because it's a highly active metal that is capable of being sacrificed. Reason why zinc is preferred for use to salt water is because of commerciality.
2. Sodium is considered as best choice to serve as cathode
3. Silicon and elephant grass sheet plates are considered the best choice as electrolyte. it also serves as storage medium
4. Aluminum foil is considered as a electron carrier
5. Fiber glass is considered as the best choice of insulator because it has a high resistance to electron passage. it will serve as electron blockage

HOW DOES IT WORKS

When electricity passes through the system, the electron in the system becomes unstable. Sodium ion is highly electronegative; the electron in sodium will pass through aluminum foil but gets trapped in the silicon and elephant grass electrolyte. Grass absorbs photon light from the sun in the process of photosynthesis but in this way the grass will store the electrons from electricity as photoelectric and also silicon is a good conductor for electricity, therefore electrons can feel comfortable in that region. Similarly the zinc will tend to sacrifice its electron because it is a highly active metal. but it will also be trapped in the electrolyte. Also fiber grass will block the electron from going out of the system till when it is needed. After it is successful charged, you can connect your phone and the electron stored in the electrolyte will charge them

DIAGRAM:

1. Insulator
2. Zinc ion
3. Aluminum foil
4. Elephant grass sheet plate
5. Silicon sheet plate
6. Sodium ion

CONCLUSION

It is efficient and covers up all the laps of the lithium ion battery. it does not affect the atmosphere and also your environment. It is very abundant on the earth. It saves cost. low maintenance and its parts can easily be replaced and is safe to use.

I want to give the honor of inspiration to the God of Heaven and Earth. And I want you to remember that Jesus loves and still loves you